

AUTHORS DETAILS

1. Mr. Alexander Eniola Akintunde (*Corresponding Author*)
B.Tech (Ogbomosho)
Email: Akintunde.alexander@gmail.com
Institution: Ladoke Akintola University of Technology
Transportation and Environmental Research Group,
Department of Civil Engineering
2. Prof. Olukorede Michael Osuolale
B.Tech (Ogbomosho), M.Sc., PhD (Ibadan),
Email: omosuolale@lautech.edu.ng
Institution: Ladoke Akintola University of Technology
Transportation and Environmental Research Group,
Department of Civil Engineering,

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TITLE: THE APPLICATION OF AGRICULTURAL WASTES TO IMPROVE LATERITIC SOIL PERFORMANCE: A REVIEW

Abstract

An effort to contribute to the actualization of global goals has necessitated finding solutions to agricultural waste, which currently creates a nuisance for the environment. This study examined the application of some agro waste in enhancing the geotechnical qualities of lateritic soils for construction purposes. The wastes taken into account are Rice Husk Ash (RHA), Bagasse Ash (BA) etc. These wastes were collected and combusted to achieve high pozzolanic at temperatures 500-8000C at a time of 1-4 hours. It was observed that the CBR, permeability characteristics, etc. of the examined wastes met the required criteria set by international standards, which affirms the efficacy of these wastes as an environmentally friendly stabilizer for construction. In addition, agro-waste with high CaO content, e.g., RHA performs best when combined with lime or cement. However, no standalone agro-waste stabilizer has yet to be explored in the studies, and therefore, recommendations are provided for future work.

Keywords: *Lateritic soil; soil stabilization; agro wastes ash; environmental sustainability; and geotechnical properties; Road Construction.*

Introduction

From a global perspective, the importance of maintaining a safe climate has grown over time. The production of inorganic pollutants like Carbon dioxide has been significantly impacted by a rising trend in soil stabilization utilizing the two common materials, cement and lime (responsible for global warming). Portland cement production releases Carbon dioxide into the environment accounting for 7% of the Carbon dioxide emission from all industrial activities on the planet come from this source (Adedokun et al., 2019). Lateritic soils are easily accessible building materials. Naturally, the makeup of lateritic differs from location to location; the amount of clay in the soil dictates its appropriateness and is controlled by how the parent rock has weathered. Due to the high clay content and poor strength, lateral soil often has a low bearing capacity and low stability in its natural form. This makes it particularly unstable when moisture is present (Alhassan, 2008). Researchers have laboriously improved the geotechnical characteristics of inappropriate lateritic soil to get the needed properties through stabilization. According to definition, laterite is a byproduct of rock decomposition that is reddish brown, yellowish, and reddish brown in form, and has a low proportion of silica and a high concentration of iron and aluminum hydroxides (Bello et al., 2013). Due to these factors, lateritic

soils must be stabilized before being used as a material of significant importance for construction. Lateritic soil with a high percentage of plastic clay damages and cracks civil engineering projects including building foundations, road pavement, and other related projects. To get the intended results of the characteristics, soil treatment through stabilization or modification may be required (Afeez et al., 2014) Instead of replacing with quality soil, which has been shown to be uneconomical, stabilizing with an addition will enhance the bad soil qualities in construction (Ojuri et al., 2014). The process of improving a soil's strength and durability so that it is suitable for construction purposes is known as soil stabilization. Since the 1970s, the price of energy has increased dramatically, driving up the cost of cement and lime, the two main conventional stabilizers (Neville, 2000). Mechanical and chemical stabilization are two different types of soil stabilization. Chemical stabilization refers to the chemical alteration between admixture (cementitious material) and the soil minerals (Pozzolanic materials) to improve the geotechnical properties of the soil. Mechanical stabilization refers to changes in the physical properties of the soil particles with the help of either energize vibrations or compaction, or both (Manasseh, 2010). The main issue with chemical stabilization, especially cement stabilization, which is the most widely used chemical stabilization, is the high cost of cement production, which has contributed to the high cost of stabilizing roads and the high carbon dioxide emissions during production (which contribute to global warming) (Czernin, 1962). Industrial-waste and agricultural-waste stabilizers are two categories of economical materials that are frequently used in developed countries to partially replace conventional stabilizers without negative consequences. Examples of these materials include palm oil frond ash, milled eggshell, bagasse ash, groundnut shell ash, bone ash, rice husk ash, iron ore tilling, and wood ash (Manasseh, 2010). As a result of the aforementioned, this work aims to evaluate the outcomes, current situation, and expected future of stabilized lateritic soil as a remedial substitute for the primary materials (cement and lime) in environmental sustainability. However, this study only chose a few of the many agricultural wastes that can be found locally in Nigeria.

2. Lateritic soil.

2.1 Definition and background studies

Dr. Francis Buchanan-Hamilton recognized laterite as a construction material used in India's Malabar region. He describes laterite as a ferruginous deposit that is "appearing unstratified and occurs not far below the surface" and has vesicular structure. The unusual property of the substance, which Buchanan first classified as laterite—from the Latin word later, which meaning brick—was that it had a soft consistency in situ but soon hardened on exposure. Due to this feature, this substance is now used as a building brick (Netterberg, 2014), as depicted in the figure 1 and 2 below. Generally speaking, laterite is a naturally weathered substance created by the accumulation of hydrated oxides of iron or aluminum. This concentration may occur by chemical precipitation, residual buildup, or solution, migration, and solution. All of these phenomena are the outcome of secondary physicochemical processes rather than the typical primary processes of sedimentation, metamorphism,

volcanism, or plutonism (Charman, 1988). They may be found on their own in an unhardened layer, or

as a component in a soil matrix or a cemented matrix encasing other materials (Amu et al., 2011).

Fig.1: Cutting of laterite bricks in quarry Fig.2: Use of laterite bricks for house construction (Netterberg, 2014)

2.2 Definition of Lateritic Soil

In essence, laterites are mixes of the original host or parent material and the authigenic cementing, replacing, or relatively accumulating minerals (mostly sesquioxides but also certain clay minerals). The authigenic mineral content rises with the development of the laterite and may eventually make up nearly all of the material. As a result, hardpan laterite is anticipated to include more sesquioxides ($Al_2O_3 + Fe_2O_3$) than nodular laterite. The chemical make-up of natural laterites is presented in Table 1. According to a study by Obianyo (2017), silicon, aluminum, and iron oxides, with respective compositions of 52.59%, 30.80%, and 7.57%, were the primary oxides found in the lateritic soil. The ratio of silica to sesquioxides (SiO_2)/ [$Fe_2O_3 + Al_2O_3$] determines whether the soil is lateritic or non-lateritic. Lateritic soil is defined as having a ratio between 1.33 and 2.00. Non-lateritic soil is defined as having a ratio greater than 2.00. In the figures below, (Oluwatuyi et al., 2018) showed the ternary diagram of the oxides of the lateritic soil while (Latifi et al., 2013) showed the SEM image of an untreated lateritic Soil.

(Oluwatuyi et al.,

Fig 3: Ternary diagram (Latifi et al., 2018)

Fig 4: SEM image of untreated soil(Latifi et al., 2013)

Table 1: Composition of lateritic material (Netterberg, 1985)

Components	% by Mass	Main form of occurrence
SiO ₂	5-70	Quartz, feldspar, clay minerals
Al ₂ O ₃	5-35	Feldspar, clay minerals, gibbsite
Fe ₂ O ₃	5-70	Goethite, hematite
TiO ₂	0-5	Anatase, rutile
MnO	0-5	?
P ₂ O ₅	0-1	Clay minerals, goethite, gibbsite
H ₂ O ⁺	5-20	Clay minerals, goethite, gibbsite
Loss on Ignition	5-30	organic matter
Organic matter	0,2-2	organic matter

2.3 Principles of the pozzolanic reactions.

Pozzolana is a silicate substance that, by itself, does not have cementitious qualities but, when finely divided in the presence of water, reacts with calcium hydroxide, Ca(OH)_2 , to create cementitious compounds. Fe_2O_3 , Al_2O_3 , SiO_2 , MgO , SO_3 , and CaO make up the majority of the pozzolana oxide composition, with a minimum of 70% Fe_2O_3 , Al_2O_3 , and SiO_2 altogether (Kadyali et al., 2008). The self-cementing characteristics of pozzolanic materials are significantly CaO -contained materials. When CaO , Al_2O_3 , and SiO_2 are combined in significant amounts while water is present, pozzolanic reactions take place. However, the presence of Al_2O_3 and SiO_2 in the material allows for the development of cement-like gels. This process involves the hydration of the CaO , which releases OH^- ions and raises pH levels to about 12.4, which is a need for pozzolanic reactions. In order to create cementitious compounds known as Calcium Silicate Hydrates (CSH) and Calcium Aluminate Hydrates, the Si and Al must combine with the calcium that is already present (CAH). Below is an overview of a condensed qualitative depiction of these reactions: (Seco et al., 2012).

3.0 Agro-Waste Stabilizer.

Environmental pollution has decreased recently as a result of the efficient use of agricultural wastes. In developing countries, ashes from agricultural wastes are the typical, affordable, and readily available materials to replace the pricy conventional stabilizers (cement and lime). and Among these wastes, Saw Dust Ash (SDA), Coconut Husk Ash (CHA), Cassava Peel Ash (CPA), Corn Cob Ash (CCA), Rice Husk Ash (RHA), Bagasse Ash (BA), Locust Bean Ash (LBA) and Oil Palm Fronds Ash (OPFA) are noteworthy (Adedokun et al., 2019). Since $\text{SiO}_2 + \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 + \text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3 = 70\% >$, these waste ashes are categorized as pozzolan. By using these waste ashes to stabilize soil, soil's geotechnical qualities have improved, reducing the amount of CO_2 emitted into the atmosphere.

3.1 Cassava Peel Ash (CPA)

The by-product of Incinerated cassava peels derived from processing cassava for domestic or industrial use is cassava peel ash (CPA) (Edeh et al., 2014). According to a study by Kemausuor et al.

(2015), two communities produce roughly 4,500 tonnes of cassava peels annually. As seen in fig. 5, the issue with cassava peel disposal has aided in the ozone layer's depletion due to human activities. For two communities, the economically viable usage of the cassava peels produced with livestock manure can generate gas with an estimated 60% methane concentration (Kemausuor et al., 2015).

Cassava Peel Ash (CPA) has a chemical composition that reveals a combined proportion of $\text{SiO}_2 + \text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3 + \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 = 71.76\%$, which is larger than 70%, demonstrating that it satisfies the ASTM criteria for an excellent pozzolan (ASTM C618, 1978). Bello et al. (2015) studied the stabilization of lateritic soil with CPA. The findings indicated that the flexibility of lateritic soil is most improved by the addition of CPA at 2%. The soil's Limit Liquid (LL) content and Plastic Limit (PL) dropped from 45% and 28% to 37.40% and 25.00%, respectively. Low plasticity is indicated by LL values of less than 35%, intermediate plasticity by values of 35% to 50%, high plasticity by values of 50% to 70%, and highly plasticity by values of $>90\%$ (Bello et al., 2015). These drops in plasticity indicators showed that the soil had improved. The value of the CBR outcomes rises as the CPA% added does. This indicates that the soil sample's strength has increased attributed to CPA. For use in the design of roads and airport runway pavement, the California Bearing Ratio (CBR) test is frequently used to determine the strength of sub-grade soil, sub-base, and base course materials. These CBR improvements meet the requirements to classify the sample as sub-grade materials (BS 1377 1990). The sample's UCS grew by the most, by 2%, when CPA was included. These outcomes provided additional confirmation of the stabilizing properties of CPA on lateritic soil when treated at the optimum level. While stabilized lateritic CPA + 5% cement soil is suitable for use as base courses, treated lateritic soil treated with cassava peel ash is only suitable for use as fill materials. CPA is a cost-effective material for road construction when used to stabilize lateritic soils in part substitute of cement. However, the environmental problem with Cassava Peels waste disposal has been resolved (Olutaiwo et al., 2016).

Chemical composition (%)								
CaO	SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	Fe ₂ O ₃	MgO	Na ₂ O	K ₂ O	SO ₃	LOI*
6.94	56.81	7.74	7.21	3.93	0.43	4.64	4.05	6.78
24.0	12.5	-	2.59	-	-	44.8	3.80	1.34
*lost of ignition								

Olutaiwo et al., 2016
Edeh et al., 2014

Fig 5: Open air burning of cassava peel (Kemausuor et al., 2015)

Table 2: Oxide percentage of Cassava Pill Ash

3.2 Rice Husk Ash (RHA).

Rice husk is a major agricultural waste product. A study found that for every 4000 kg of rice, 1000 kg of rice husk is produced, and this waste contributes roughly 15-20% of its weight in the form of ash. According to (Sekifuji et al., 2019), rice husks are easily accessible and can be used to produce an appropriate kind of renewable energy, resulting in the development of a sustainable society. The release

into

waste

1978).

of hazardous oxide the environment is facilitated by the frequent piling and/or burning of rice husk during the milling process (Beagle E.C.,

Fig 6: Rice Husk (Beagle E.C., 1978).

According to Jha et al. (2006), Alhassan (2008), and Afolayan et al. 2019, the ash has been classified as a pozzolana, making it a class "F" pozzolan, which denotes that it is a good pozzolan (ASTM C618, 1978). The combustion conditions (burning length, temperature, cooling time, and burning type) of RHA determine its quality and will have an impact on how effective it is at improving the geotechnical qualities of the soil. High pozzolanic is best achieved at temperatures 500-8000C and time of 1-4 hours (Guyen et al., 2020). The high percentage of siliceous materials in RHA, as shown in Table 3, clearly indicates that it has pozzolanic properties. However, because it lacks cementitious properties, RHA is ineffective and inefficient as a standalone stabilizer. However, it could be combined with other agricultural waste that has potential cementitious properties.

Table 3: Chemical composition of RHA (Afolayan *et al.*, 2019)

Chemical Composition (%)								
SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	Fe ₂ O ₃	CaO	MgO	SO ₃	Na ₂ O	K ₂ O	LOI
82.14	1.34	1.27	1.21	1.96	0.17	0.14	2.09	-
90.80	3.5	1.32	1.57	1.20	-	0.15	0.24	0.67
97.10	1.14	0.32	0.07	0.83	0.15	0.09	0.18	0.97
77.27	3.59	9.82	8.95	5.85	-	2.90	4.08	4.84
95.41	0.00	0.82	0.00	1.24	0.07	0.22	1.65	-
68.12	1.06	0.78	1.01	1.31	0.14	-	21.23	18.25

A series of laboratory experiments were done on lateritic A-7-6 grouped soil to see how well-burned rice husk ash affected the geotechnical characteristics of lateritic soil. The findings showed that while the plasticity index and maximum dry density decreased with increasing RHA content, the liquid limit, plastic limit, optimal moisture content, unconfined compressive strength, California bearing ratio value, cohesion, shear strength, and angle of internal friction all increased linearly (Rahman et al., 1986).

The RHA's non-plasticity and water absorption capabilities may cause the soil mixtures' plasticity indices to drop (Nguyen et al., 2020). According to the author, the combination of ash with fine-grained cohesive soil has a flocculation effect that lowers the soil's plasticity index. It is noteworthy that the optimum RHA concentration necessary to economically stabilize the lateritic soil sample for sub-base materials in highway construction was identified as 17% RHA content. The UCS, CBR, and shear strength parameters of the sample treated were maximum around 17% RHA content. Without making any observations on other pavement structures (Base, subgrade) stabilized with RHA content, the study exclusively examined sub-base materials for road construction. The optimization of the strength characteristics, such as UCS, CBR, and shear strength, occurred at a certain level of RHA content (Nguyen et al., 2020). As the RHA content rises above the threshold level, the strength metrics drop. (Akinyele et al., 2015) applied RHA to stabilize lateritic clay soil and found that a subgrade stabilized with a RHA level of no more than 10% works well for road construction. The plasticity index (PI) values decreased from 21 to 10.7% as a result of the results, which showed that the liquid limit is between 34 and 41.5% and the plastic limit is between 13-28%. A drop in the plasticity index indicates an improvement in soil quality. According to the author, RHA is an appropriate material for hydraulic barriers since treated soil with a greater liquid limit will have lower hydraulic conductivities. The stabilised soil's strength characteristic (CBR, USC value) was not evaluated in the study. In order to improve soil, RHA is frequently mixed with chemical binders like lime and/or cement due to its low cementitious properties (Nguyen et al., 2020). The impact of cement-RHA combination on lateritic soil was investigated by (Rahman et al., 1987). According to the study, the ideal mixtures for sub base and base are 6% RHA + 3% cement and 6% RHA + 6% cement, respectively. (Alhassan et al., 2008) studied the effect of RHA combined with cement. The results showed a noticeable improvement in the CBR (Figure 7) and UCS (Figure 8) with increase in the RHA content at specified cement amounts, with 4 and 6% RHA being the ideal values.

Fig 7: Variation of CBR with RHA content

Fig 8: Variation of 28 days UCS with RHA content

(Alhassan et al., 2008)

The UCS values also show an increase in strength with curing age, suggesting the possibility of utilizing 4 and 6% RHA in an admixture with less cement for laterite soil stabilization. The study's focus is on base and sub-base materials for use in highway construction. In a further study, (Alhassan. 2008) the potentials of solely RHA on an A-7-6 lateritic soil stabilized with 2-12% (RHA) by weight of the dry soil were assessed. The results showed that when RHA content increased, the maximum dry density (MDD) generally decreased and the optimum moisture content (OMC) generally moved upward. With an increase in RHA content, there was also a modest improvement in the CBR (Figure 9) and UCS (Figure 10). Peak UCS values were observed at 6-8% RHA, suggesting limited possibility for A-7-6 lateritic soil strength increase at this RHA level. The author came to the conclusion that Cement + RHA for soil treatment is superior to RHA alone after comparing the strength parameter of soil from (Rahman 1987).

Fig 9: Variation of CBR with RHA content Fig

10: Variation of UCS with RHA content

(Alhassan. 2008)

3.3 Coconut Shell Ash (CSA) & Coconut Husk Ash (CHA)

The coconut palm (*Cocos nucifera* L.) is a useful and adaptable crop with many applications. If heated to an appropriate temperature, the husk and shell are effective energy sources. As a result, coconut shells have little to no commercial value, and their disposal has greatly degraded the ecosystem (Oluremi et al., 2016). For CHA, the overall oxide composition fraction of silica (SiO₂), alumina (Al₂O₃), and iron oxide (Fe₂O₃) was 73.35%. (Adedokun et al., 2019). CSA and CHA are pozzolanic materials because the addition of the oxides of silicon, aluminum, and iron is greater than 70%. (ASTM C618, 1978). Additionally, the loss on ignition of CHA (9.34) was less than the maximum 12% specified by ASTM C618 (2005). According to a recent study, the X-ray fluorescence analyzer was used to assess the oxide composition of CSA; the sum of the oxide compositions of Fe₂O₃, SiO₂, and Al₂O₃ is above 70%. (Ramli et al., 2021). The sum of the pozzolanic oxides identified in CSA, according to a different study by Olugbenga et al. (2011), is 6.03%, which does meet the criterion for pozzolan (ASTM C618 2005). Strength Development in Lateritic Soil Stabilized with CSA for Highway Pavement Construction was the subject of another study by Oluremi et al. (2016). The liquid limit, plastic limit, and plasticity index (Figure 8) all significantly decrease as CSA content increases, from 50.2 to 28%, 43.8 to 24%, and 6.5 to 4%, respectively. This indicates that the soil is less susceptible to water. The soil was treated with 3 to 12% CSA. With a rise in CSA content, the strength measure, CBR, declines. The results, however, did not meet the stipulated limitations of 35% maximum for percentage passing through sieve No. 200, 30% maximum for liquid limits, and 12% maximum for plasticity index for sub-base and base materials, according to the author (Road and Bridges Specification, 1997). The author asserts that treated soil could be used as a fill material for subgrade, but (figure 11) shows that the optimum value for the LL and PI is at 12% CSA content,

giving the values of 28% and 4%, respectively. Due to the decrease in the strength parameter of the treated soil, CSA is unsuitable as a stand-alone stabilizer and for improving soils with high liquid limit; rather, it should be used in conjunction with other conventional stabilizers, such as cement or lime. Similar research examined the impact of coconut shell ash (CSA) on lateritic soil treated with lime for road construction (Nnochiri et al., 2017). The best value is shown in table 5 by the results of the CBR and UCS. It is noteworthy that the Plasticity Index (PI) value drops as the CSA content increases; the PI value was at its highest at the 4% lime + 4% CSA mixture, which was 14.3%. The author came to the conclusion that lime combined with CSA achieves sufficient strength as opposed to CSA used as a standalone stabilizer. Oluremi et al. (2012) evaluated the soil sample stabilized using 0, 2, 4, 6, 8 and 10% of coconut husk ash (CHA) by mass of soil sample in order to determine the influence of CHA on the stabilization of poor lateritic soil deposit. The ranges for the liquid limit, plastic limit, and plasticity index are, respectively, (58.9-65), (25-47.14%), and (16.71-37%). The results demonstrate that CHA is ineffectual to stabilize lateritic soils with high liquid limit, with liquid limits of 30% maximum and plasticity index of 10% maximum being the Road and Bridges Specification, 1997 standards for sub-base and base materials. The author concluded that CHA is suitable to improve lateritic soils with low CBR values by observing that the soil strength parameter increases with the addition of CHA in (figure 12).

Fig 11: Variation of atterberg limits with CSA content Fig 12: Relationship between CBR values and CHA Content (%) (Oluremi et al., 2012)

Table 4: Oxide percentage of (CHA) and (CSA)

Chemical composition (%)

CaO	SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	Fe ₂ O ₃	MgO	Na ₂ O	K ₂ O	SO ₃	LOI *	
0.29	72.31	0.86	0.18	0.02	-	4.47	-	9.34	(Oyediran et al., 2015)
8.76	17.9	-	4.65	-	-	-	1.4	-	CHA (Oluremi et al., 2012)
6.26	4.46	1.39	1.32	15.42	45.01	5.75	-	5.0	CHA (Olugbenga et al., 2011)
4.98	37.97	24.12	15.48	1.89	0.95	0.83	0.71	11.94	CSA (Ramli, et al., 2021)
		*Lost	of	ignition					CSA

Table 5: Atterberg Limit tests results for CSA- Lime stabilization (Nnochiri et al., 2017)

% lime by weight	% CSA by weight	LL %	PL %	PI %	MDD %	OMC %	CBR (unsoaked)	UCS (kN/m ²)
0	0	49.4	13.3	36.1	1398	17.42		57.30
1	7	59.1	28.0	31.1				
2	6	65.3	37.3	28.0				
3	5	55.5	34.9	20.6				
4	4	51.4	37.1	14.3				
5	3	53.8	36.7	17.1	1387		25.35	242.89
6	2	54.7	36.4	18.3				
7	1	52.6	35.7	16.9				

In a related study, (Olugbenga et al., 2011) investigated the geotechnical characteristics of three lateritic soils (A, B, and C) amended with coconut shell and husk ash (CSHA) contents. The Plasticity Index (PI) of samples A, B, and C decreases from 20.43 to 16.74%, 20.20 to 18%, and 29.51 to 15.67%, respectively, between 2-4% CSHA concentration. A decrease in PI decreases the swelling ability, leading to an increase in strength attributes. According to the author, shear strengths increased at 4% CSHA and CBR values subsequently increased with higher CSHA contents. It was found that ash from coconut husks and shells can enhance lateritic soils' geotechnical characteristics. (Vysakh et al., 2012) Investigated the suitability of coconut shell, husk and leaf ash (CSLHA) to stabilize the lateritic soil, it was observed that the Liquid Limit (LL) value decreases from 49.6% to 40% as the CSLHA content increases (0-7) % and then it increases from 40% to 47% between CSLHA content (7-9)%, hence 7% is the optimal % which gives the LL value 40%. The Plasticity Index (PI) of the soil reduces with increase in CSLHA content up to 7% and then it increase. The author stated that the PI reduction is due to flocculation of clay particle in the soil as a result of pozzolanic action of CSLHA. The experiment clearly showed that the CBR strength is best at 7% CSLHA for both unsoaked and soaked conditions, hence it was determined that 7% CSLHA is the most advantageous amount to be

added for road construction. It is important to note that when comparing the chemical composition of coconut husk ash (CHA) and coconut shell ash (CSA), which has been the subject of previous studies by Oluremi et al. (2012), Adedokun et al. (2019), Oluremi et al. (2020), and Nnochiri et al. (2017), it is possible to find more calcium oxide (Cao), which is the main oxide that affects strength in conventional Therefore, CHA is a better stabilizer than CSA, according to the results of the summary above.

3.4 Baggase Ash (BA)

Bagasse is the fiber byproduct obtained from sugarcane following the extraction of sugar juice at the mill factory (Sadeeq et al., 2015). (Okonkwo et al., 2016). The environment is dangerously affected by the indiscriminate disposal of bagasse from the sugar industry and human activity (Osinubi et al., 2009). If it is not disposed of properly or used for commercial purposes (as stabilizer) or in the paper industry, the residue causes bagassosis, a chronic respiratory condition (Technology et al., 2017). When bagasse is incinerated at a controlled temperature, bagasse ash (BA) is produced. According to Okonkwo et al. (2016) and Usman et al. (2014), bagasse ash burned at 700°C has silica and alumina levels up to 77.29% and 10.95%, respectively. This confirms BA's suitability as a pozzolanic material. According to research (Sadeeq et al., 2015), burning at temperatures that encourage the growth of crystalline (less reactive) rather than amorphous (more reactive) particles is the main cause of pozzolans like BA losing their pozzolalic activity. According to the author, the pozzolanic reactivity of BA is substantially influenced by the incinerating temperature, reaching its peak at 500°C.

Fig 13: Indiscriminate disposal of bagasse in the environment (Technology et al., 2017)

Chemical composition (%)								
CaO	SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	Fe ₂ O ₃	MgO	Na ₂ O	K ₂ O	SO ₃	LOI *
10.01	43.32	2.67	1.17	1.85	0.04	17.41	5.89	10.37

(Osinubi et al.,)

4.52	57.95	8.23	3.96	4.47	-	2.41	-	5.0	2013) <i>Sadeeq et al., 2015</i>	Table 6: Oxide percentage of bag
1.78	65.58	5.87	4.32	1.23	1.02	6.41	0.18	10.48	(Hailu et al., 2011)	
11.16	65.27	3.11 *Lost	2.1 of	1.27 ignition	-	-	-	2.21	(Anupam et al., 2013)	

asse Ash (BA)

(Salahudeen et al., 2015) investigated how bagasse ash (BA) affected lateritic soil's engineering properties and found that the consistency limits test did not reveal any appreciable improvements over the original soil. At 2% BA content, the liquid and plastic limits rose by 36.32 - 38.00% and 21.30 - 21.54%, respectively. The plasticity index value was below the 12% threshold that was required for sub-base materials (Road and Bridges Specification., 1997). According to the author, when examined at MDD and OMC, the unsoaked CBR for soil treated with BA content of 4% and higher met the minimum CBR value of 30% defined by (BS 1377., 1990) for materials appropriate for use as base course material. While soaked CBR met the value recommended by Gidigas et al. (1990), who stated that a minimum CBR value of 20%–30% is required for sub-bases when compacted at OMC, the optimum unsoaked and value of 62% recorded at 8% BA content was below the 80% CBR value recommended by Road and Bridges Specification. In a related study, (Sadeeq et al., 2015) assessed the effect of BA on lateritic soils treated with lime. The author asserted that higher lime concentration increased CBR values because there was enough calcium present to generate the primary compounds that increase strength, calcium silicate hydrate (CSH) and calcium aluminate hydrate (CAH). The highest UCS and CBR values, 698 kN/m² and 43%, were found in soil treated with 8% lime/6% BA. For materials compacted at the ideal moisture content, the highest CBR value satisfied the 20–30% criteria for sub-base given by (Gidigas et al., 1980). To examine the plasticity and particle size

distribution characteristics of BA on laterite treated with cement, another study (Mu'azu 2007) treated lateritic soil with 1-4% cement contents combined with 2-8% BA content. Figure 10 depicts a considerable drop in the percentage of fines from 63% to almost zero (BS Sieve No. 200). While the plastic limit increased, the liquid limit and plasticity index decreased. The (Road and Bridges Specification, 1997) for direct use as pavement material are not met in any of the BA contents considered, but the grain size requirement were met with respect to the percentage passing BS sieve No. 200. The recommended percentage of BA should be between 4% and 6%, the author concluded from the consideration. According to a research article, 8% of BA content is the ideal level to provide the highest CBR value, and the value declined as the amount of bagasse ash in the mixture increased (Rajakumar et al., 2014). (Figure 15).

Fig 14: Variation of particle size distribution with BA content with 1% cement (Beagle E.C., 1978)

Fig 15: Relationship between CBR values and BA Content (%) (Rajakumar et al., 2014)

3.5 Groundnut Shell Ash (GSA)

An agricultural waste product from the milling sector and landfills is groundnut shell. According to (Moreno et al., 2018), the groundnut industry is a significant generator of agro-waste that is typically disposed of and can be used to make biomass for electricity. Pozzolana is the term used to describe the shell that burned at atmospheric temperature (Rajakumar et al., 2014). (Salahudeen et al., 2018). Because groundnut shells are difficult to dispose of as waste, researchers are using them as substitute in the construction sector (Salahudeen et al., 2018). The elemental oxides found in the GSA according to different investigations are listed in Table 7 along with their corresponding weight compositions in percentages. According to observations, GSA has a significant amount of CaO, indicating that it has self-cementing properties. Depending on the burning conditions, this causes the overall percentage of Fe₂O₃, Al₂O₃, and SiO₂ to range from 40 to 70%.

Fig 16: Groundnut Shell (Moreno et al., 2018)

Table 7: Oxide percentage of Groundnut Shell Ash (GSA)

Chemical composition (%)								
CaO	SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	Fe ₂ O ₃	MgO	Na ₂ O	K ₂ O	SO ₃	LOI *
25.44	20.45	2.21	6.08	3.12	-	22.93	1.00	6.21
15.63	51.54	22.45	2.40	1.20	0.04	-	0.05	3.05
15.63	51.54	22.45	2.40	1.20	0.94	-	-	3.98
			*lost	of	ignition			

The geotechnical characteristics of A-2-6 group lateritic soil stabilized by adding GSA 2, 4, 6, 8, and 10% by weight of the soil were evaluated by (Nnochiri et al., 2018). At 10% GHA by weight of soil, the liquid limit (LL) and plasticity index (PI) values significantly decreased from (36.50 - 31.20)% and (19.30 - 16.48)%, respectively. However, the optimal value is at 8% GSA content for both LL and PI. According to the author, replacing soil fines with GHA, which has a lower affinity for water, may have reduced the LL and PI value, which would indicate that the treated soil's compressibility and swelling qualities had decreased. The CBR and UCS values rise from (24.42-72.88)% and (510.25-1186.46) kN/m², respectively, for 0–10% GSA by soil weight. A possible explanation for this rise is the gradual development of cementitious compounds in the soil as a result of the reaction between the GSA and a little quantity of calcium hydroxide (CaO) that is present in the soil. According to the author, GSA serves the purpose of a subgrade and subbase in road building adequately as an economic stabilizer. (Rajakumar et al., 2014) observed that the optimal percentage for giving the highest CBR value is 8% of GSA content, and that this percentage decreases when GSA content is increased further (Figure 17). Similar studies evaluated the impact of GSA on lime-stabilized lateritic soil (nnochiri, 2017). The author found that adding GHA to lime-stabilized soil increased the release of Ca²⁺ and Si²⁺ cat ions, which considerably decreased the soil's liquid limit and plasticity index values. This shows that the soil's qualities have improved, making it suitable for use as a subbase material in Nigerian roadways (Road and Bridges Specification, 1997).

Fig 17: Relationship between CBR values and GSA Content (%) (Rajakuma et al., 2014)

3.6 Bone Ash powder (BAP)

Bone is a tissue made primarily of hydroxyapatite, however it may also contain carbonate. Animal bones are calcined to produce bone ash, which is a grey-white powdered ash predominantly composed of calcium phosphate (Adetayo et al., 2019). (Obianyo et al., 2020). based on research into the chemical makeup of bone ash. Dogfish bones have the highest value level of calcium (37%), whereas cow bones have the major oxide composition for strength gain (36.05%), according to Morgulis (1931). The results of the chemical analysis test of the bone ash from earlier research are shown in Table 8 below. It was discovered that the principal oxides in the bone ash are CaO and P₂O₅. Fe₂O₃, SiO₂, and Al₂O₃ make up less than the minimum of 70% required for pozzolan, according to (ASTM C618, 1978) standard. Using lime and bone ash, (Obianyo et al., 2020) increased the strength of lateritic soil. According to the author, the ideal amounts of hydrated lime and bone ash addition for soil stability are 9% and 5% by weight, respectively. Additionally, (Ayininuola et al., 2014) investigated how bone ash affected the soil's California bearing ratio (CBR). The findings showed that the CBR value increased with the addition of bone ash up to 7% before gradually declining after that. Soil CBR of subgrade or road base can be improved by adding bone ash at a maximum of 7%.

Table 8: Oxide percentage of Bone Ash Powder

Chemical composition (%)								
CaO	SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	Fe ₂ O ₃	MgO	Na ₂ O	K ₂ O	SO ₃	LOI *
45.53	0.09	0.06	0.1	1.18	-	-	-	-
52.2	-	0.61	0.03	2.07	1.32	0.09	-	-
48.21	0.12	0.08	0.09	1.29	-	6.41	-	0.21
			*lost	of	ignition			

4. Current stage and future prospect of Agro-waste stabilizer.

There is currently a serious environmental issue facing the entire world. Public concerns include the management of domestic and commercial waste, environmental sustainability, and ozone layer protection (Foo et al., 2009). The use of agro-waste for stabilizing lateritic soil for various construction uses in Nigeria and other African nations has been motivated by the necessity to utilize viable construction material that is Sustainable, affordable, and easily accessible. The use of chemicals produced industrially has maintained the price of constructing stabilized roads high. This has discouraged emerging and underdeveloped countries from constructing accessible roads for their rural communities, which frequently make up the bulk of the population and rely heavily on agriculture for a living (Adeboje et al., 2016). There are now a number of approaches for strengthening expansive soils. These techniques include surcharge loading, thermal approaches, rewetting, compaction regulation, moisture control, soil replacement, and stabilization using chemical additives. However, these techniques are expensive, so there is a need for an affordable and efficient soil stabilizer (Ramaji, 2012).

Agro-waste has been successfully employed to stabilize and treat lateritic soils for a variety of civil engineering purposes, according to research done in the past. This is accomplished by either mixing these wastes with conventional materials (such as cement or lime) or applying them alone in a refined form (such as ash), which enhances the soil's characteristics. However, using agro-waste to ameliorate soil materials will help attain the sustainable development goal. The usage of these waste materials will address the problem of waste disposal and lower the cost of roadway and landfill construction. Due to the combination of SiO_2 , Al_2O_3 , and Fe_2O_3 content present, which is responsible for their behavior as a modifier and stabilizer, the agricultural wastes considered, RHA>BA>CHA>CPA>CSA>GSA> BAP in terms of pozzolanity (Afolayan et al.,2019). Recent studies have shown that using conventional stabilizing agents might cause serious issues as carbonation, sulfate attack, and ecological damage. Thus, a remedy to some of the serious drawbacks of employing cement or lime for soil stability is suggested: magnesium oxide/hydroxide (Jawad et al., 2014). sTaking into account the aforementioned drawbacks, it was discovered that agricultural wastes such as bone ash, rice husk ash, eggshell powder, and palm kernel shell had been discovered to have excellent oxide composition and could be used as pozzolan (Oluwatuyi et al., 2018), (Adeboje et al., 2016). Pozzolanic reactions, on the other hand, depend on time and take a long time (years) to strengthen sufficiently since they are dependent on temperature, the amount of calcium present, the pH level, and the proportion of silica and alumina in the soil minerals.

5. Conclusion and future recommendation

The literature that is currently accessible was reviewed to determine whether it is feasible to use agro-waste to stabilize lateritic soil for construction purposes. The outcomes of these studies suggest that agro-waste may be blended with cement and lime to improve soil. Based on the reviewed literature, the following conclusions and suggestions can be made:

1. The plasticity and UCS of lateritic soil are improved most by the addition of CPA at 2%. The stabilized lateritic soil mixed with CPA + 5% cement, on the other hand, will be suitable for use as base courses while CPA alone will be suitable for fill materials.
2. It is established that pozzolanitic is best achieved between 500 and 8000 °C and during calcinations lasting one to four hours. The quality of the agro-waste stabilizer is determined by

the combustion condition (burning length, temperature, cooling time, and burning type), which also affects how well it improves the geotechnical features of the soil.

3. A suitable stabilizer for subgrade in road construction is RHA content that is no higher than 10%, while the ideal RHA content for sub-base materials is 17%.
4. No agro-waste that is suitable as a standalone stabilizer has been found, however they work well when mixed with a conventional stabilizer (such as lime or cement) to produce a sufficient amount of strength.
5. The ideal CSLHA addition rate for constructing roads is discovered to be 7%. Considering the oxide composition, CHA is a better stabilizer than CSA when it comes to lateritic soils with low CBR values.
6. The optimal GSA content to achieve the highest CBR value is 8%; nevertheless, GSA that has been mixed with a conventional stabilizer (lime or cement) is suitable for usage as subbase material in Nigerian roads.
7. Agro-waste ash's set time properties are influenced by CaO, Al₂O₃, SO₃, and Na₂O.
8. Animal waste for stabilization has received little to no attention in previous research, which has focused primarily on agricultural waste from plants. Therefore, it is advised that animal waste with a high Cao concentration be investigated in further research as a potential replacement for traditional stabilizer (such as cement or lime).

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